

**AN EFFICIENT TIME-DOMAIN FATIGUE ANALYSIS AND ITS COMPARISON TO
SPECTRAL FATIGUE ASSESSMENT FOR CONSTRUCTION STEEL 10HNAP**

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Abstract

In the present paper, the capability of two multiaxial fatigue criteria in both estimating the fatigue life and predicting the crack initiation path of metallic components under random loading is investigated. As a matter of fact, it is very difficult to find in the literature the predicted crack initiation path data when the loading has a random nature. To such an aim, an experimental campaign performed at the Opole University of Technology on a construction steel 10HNAP, under biaxial non-proportional random loading, is simulated by means of both a time-domain criterion and a frequency-domain one.

Keywords

biaxial random loading; crack initiation path orientation; fatigue life; frequency-domain criterion; time-domain criterion

1. INTRODUCTION

Mechanical parts are often subjected to random loading during operational conditions. Due to random loading, such parts experiment a local random stress state that can be uniaxial or multiaxial. This is the case, for example, of: steel coil springs [1-4] and lower arms [5,6] in the suspension system of vehicles that experience fatigue loading during operation due to random road excitations, railway axles [7-11] and automotive crankshafts [12-14] subjected to typical rotating bending loading, and turbine bladed disks [15-17] excited by fluid flow.

Due to the fact that 80% to 95% of mechanical parts fail due to fatigue (based on industrial data), it is crucial that fast and effective tools are available to estimate lifetime during the design process, before the mechanical structure/component is used in natural working environment.

In such a context, a well-established practice of fatigue assessment under random loading consists in: (i) determination of the loading history, (ii) identification of loading cycles making damage, (iii) evaluation of the total fatigue damage by aggregating the above contributions [18]. The available algorithms for such an assessment can be categorised into two groups: time-domain and frequency-domain methods.

In time-domain, the loading of the material is represented by the time course of stresses and/or strains. The identification of cycles

of the random loading is performed by using numerical methods for cycles counting. Among them, the rainflow counting method is usually employed [19]. The fatigue life is calculated based on the fatigue performance curve of the material and a fatigue cumulative damage theory. Among such theories, the Palmgren-Miner linear accumulation theory is usually employed [20,21].

The combination of the rainflow counting method and Palmgren-Miner rule has been thoroughly tested, and it is generally accepted as one of the best time-domain method for fatigue assessment under random loading [18]. However, although the development in computer science and hardware has accelerated calculations, the computational time of the existing algorithms is high, especially when the time histories of sample points to process come from finely discretised 3D FE models, characterised by a huge number of nodes.

In frequency-domain, the material loading is represented by the frequency characteristics of stresses and/or strains, that is by their power spectral density function. An immediate advantage is related to FE models, where the frequency response calculations are faster with respect to transient dynamic analysis in time domain [18]. The fatigue life is calculated based on a method for estimating damage. Among such methods, the Dirlik's empirical formula is the most widely used [22].

Since most Authors consider the rainflow counting method to be the most accurate, the frequency-domain methods try to obtain a cycle distribution according to the above method [18].

In the present paper, two multiaxial criteria, proposed by some of the present authors in the recent past, are considered: one is formulated in time-domain [23-26], based on the critical plane approach and derived for stationary ergodic Gaussian process, whereas the other is the reformulation of the above one in frequency-domain [23,26-29].

The aim of this paper is to show the capability of the above criteria to estimate the fatigue life, as well as to predict crack initiation path in metallic materials, being such an orientation estimation lacking in many research works available in the literature. To such an aim, an experimental campaign performed at the Opole University of Technology on a construction steel 10HNAP, under biaxial non-proportional random loading, is analysed [30].

The paper is structured as follows. In **Section 2** the material characterisation, and the description of the specimens and the testing procedure are presented, together with the experimental findings. In **Section 3** the time-domain method employed to simulate the above tests is described, whereas in **Section 4** the reformulation of the above one in the frequency domain is presented. **Section 5** is dedicated to the presentation and discussion of the results obtained by applying the above criteria to the experimental data presented in Section 2, together with their comparison with both the experimental measurements and the theoretical results obtained by employing some time-domain criteria available in the literature. The main conclusions are summarised in **Section 6**.

2. EXPERIMENTS

The experimental campaign here examined was performed at the Opole University of Technology [30] and here briefly summarised.

2.1 Material

The material investigated was a construction steel 10HNAP, included in the EN 10125-1 [31] and 10125-5 [32] European Standards that regulate low-alloyed and corrosion resistant steels. Such a steel is a low-alloy high-strength steel, used for building and welded structures, with a high resistance to atmospheric corrosion.

The chemical composition of the material is reported in **Table 1**, whereas its tensile and fatigue properties are listed in **Table 2**.

Table 1.

Table 2.

The average grain size was equal to 22.5 μ m. A metallography of the material is shown in **Figure 1**: a typical fine grained ferritic-perlitic microstructure is recognised, where the light grains are the ferrite ones, whereas the dark grains are the perlite ones.

Figure 1.

2.2 Specimens manufacturing and geometry

The specimens were cut from a 10HNAP sheet with a thickness equal to 16mm, being the thickness direction that of the rolling. The circular cross-section specimens, which geometry sizes are shown in **Figure 2**, were manufactured by turning, followed by a conventional

polishing of the surface using progressively finer emery papers. A final roughness equal to 0.16 μ m was obtained.

Figure 2.

2.3 Test equipment and procedure

The testing stand MZGS-200PL, shown in **Figure 3** and developed at the Opole University of Technology [30,33-35], was used to perform the fatigue tests under random non-proportional combined bending and torsion.

Figure 3.

Each of such moments was obtained as the results of a lever motion in vertical direction, being the motion generated by the inertial force of an unbalance mass on the four rotating disks mounted on flat springs. In correspondence of such disks there were some weights and, due to the rotational movement, they produced the vibration of both the springs and the levers, transferring the loading to the specimen that was fixed in a grip.

The power unit was composed by two three-phase asynchronous motors of 0.18kW.

The stand was equipped by a full Wheatstone bridge, mounted on each lever. The electric signal was sent from the strain gauges (with a resistance equal to 120 Ω) to the extensometer bridge, then

to the spectrum analyser, and finally transformed in a moment time history and registered on a computer hard disk.

The frequency on the specimen was measured by using the spectrum analyser of the digital system.

Details of the fatigue testing stand MZGS-200PL may be found in Ref. [32].

The loading was characterised by a dominant frequency equal to 28.8Hz for bending and 30.0Hz for torsion. The random time histories of the above moments were independent, and obtained as the sum of four harmonic components characterised by different amplitude, frequency and phase-shift.

Thirteen loading conditions were considered, being characterised by: a loading ratio, defined as the ratio between the maximum normal stress, $\sigma_{z,max}$, and the maximum shear stress, $\tau_{yz,max}$, ($\lambda = \sigma_{z,max} / \tau_{yz,max}$), a cross-correlation coefficient between the normal and shear stress ($r_{\sigma_z \tau_{yz}} = \mu_{\sigma_z \tau_{yz}} / \sqrt{\mu_{\sigma_z} \mu_{\tau_{yz}}}$) equal to 0.16, and an irregular index equal to 0.99 for bending and equal to 0.97 for torsion. For each loading condition examined, the number of tests performed is listed in **Table 3**, together with the standard deviation of the normal, $\sqrt{\mu_{\sigma_z}}$, and shear, $\sqrt{\mu_{\tau_{yz}}}$, stress signals.

Table 3.

For the above loading conditions, the Probability Density Functions (PDFs) of σ_z and τ_{yz} are shown in **Figure 4**, being related to an observation period, T_0 , equal to 900s.

Figure 4.

2.4 Results

Table 3 summarises the results of the experimental campaign [30], in terms of both fatigue life, T_{exp} , and orientation of the normal to the crack initiation path, α_{exp} . Such an orientation is firstly obtained from the digitalisation of the crack paths related to the different specimens tested under the same loading condition, and then interpolation of such points by a straight line in order to compute an average crack initiation path [30]. The scatter band of the actual crack paths, measured with respect to the above interpolating line, is reported in brackets in **Table 3**, for each loading condition examined.

3. TIME-DOMAIN CRITERION

The main steps of the present time-domain criterion [23-26] are depicted in **Figure 5**. In particular, by taking as starting point the fundamentals of the Carpinteri et al. fatigue criterion for constant amplitude cyclic loading (see for instance Refs [36-39]), the fatigue damage assessment is hereafter performed at a material point P (located on the component surface) by considering an equivalent uniaxial stress related to the so-called critical plane.

In order to perform the fatigue analysis, some input data are required, and more precisely:

- the fatigue material properties, that is: the fatigue strength under fully reversed normal stress, $\sigma_{af,-1}$, at the reference number of loading cycles, N_0 , the inverse slope of the S-N curve under fully reversed normal stress, k , ($\sigma^k N = C_\sigma$) and the fatigue strength under fully reversed shear stress, $\tau_{af,-1}$;
- the applied loading conditions, that is: the time histories of both the normal stress, $\sigma_z(t)$, and the shear stress, $\tau_{yz}(t)$, registered during the experimental tests.

The main steps of the present criterion are discussed in detail in the following Sub-Sections.

Figure 5.

3.1 Critical plane determination

The orientation of the critical plane (that is, the verification plane) is assumed coincident with the crack initiation direction and is correlated with the principal stress directions. Readers may find more details about the above assumptions in Ref. [40].

In order to determine such an orientation, let us consider a fixed frame XYZ with its origin in P (**Figure 5**). The principal stresses $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$ (with $\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \sigma_3$) and the corresponding principal directions $1, 2, 3$ (identified through the principal Euler angles ϕ, θ, ψ

) can be easily determined. However, 1,2,3 are usually time varying in presence of multiaxial cyclic loading and, consequently, Carpinteri et al. [40] proposed to compute the averaged principal stress directions ($\hat{1}, \hat{2}, \hat{3}$) by averaging the principal Euler angles ($\hat{\phi}, \hat{\theta}, \hat{\psi}$) on the loading cycle T by means of the following relationships (**Figure 5**):

$$\hat{\phi} = \frac{1}{W_0} \int_0^T \phi(t) W(t) dt \quad \hat{\theta} = \frac{1}{W_0} \int_0^T \theta(t) W(t) dt \quad \hat{\psi} = \frac{1}{W_0} \int_0^T \psi(t) W(t) dt \quad (1)$$

where:

$$W = \int_0^T W(t) dt \quad \text{with} \quad W(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \sigma_1(t) < \sigma_{1,max} \\ 1, & \sigma_1(t) = \sigma_{1,max} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

being $W(t)$ the weight function, $\sigma_{1,max}$ the maximum value of σ_1 during the observation time interval T_0 .

Subsequently, the normal \mathbf{w} to the critical plane is linked to the $\hat{1}$ - direction through an off-angle δ defined as follows (**Figure 5**):

$$\delta = \frac{3}{2} \left[1 - (\tau_{af,-1} / \sigma_{af,-1})^2 \right] 45^\circ \quad (3)$$

Note that, the above rotation is performed in the plane $\hat{1}\hat{3}$, being $\hat{3}$ the averaged direction of the minimum principal stress.

3.2 Reduction of the time histories of the stress components on the critical plane

Once the critical plane, Δ , is determined, a local frame uvw with its origin in P is adopted (see the red frame in **Figure 5**), where:

- the u -axis is represented by the intersection line between Δ and the plane identified by w and Z -axis;
- the v -axis forms an orthogonal frame with u - and w -axis.

The angle between the u -axis and the averaged principal stress direction $\hat{2}$ is named γ .

At each time instant t of the fatigue loading history, the stress vector \mathbf{S}_w related to the above Δ orientation is decomposed in two components: the normal stress vector, \mathbf{N} , (perpendicular to the critical plane) and the shear stress vector, \mathbf{C} , (lying on the critical plane).

Provided that the sampling frequency is greater than the highest frequency component of the applied loading history, $N(t)$ and $C(t)$ can be treated as discrete variables (named in the following N_i and C_i), where each series is composed by n elements ($1 \leq i \leq n$). Moreover, the \mathbf{C} series may be decomposed in two components along the u - and v -axis, named $C_{u,i}$ and $C_{v,i}$, respectively.

Subsequently, the original \mathbf{N} -series is reduced by eliminating the i -th values corresponding to non-extreme ones (that is, only

peaks and valleys are preserved), and a new N_j^* -series, characterised by the same temporal duration of the original one, is obtained.

A further reduction procedure is also performed on the \mathbf{C} -series, by preserving the maximum value of the amplitude of \mathbf{C} inside a time interval bounded by two instants corresponding to a peak and a valley of the \mathbf{N} -series. In particular, new series of the \mathbf{C} components are obtained (named in the following $C_{u,j}^*$ and $C_{v,j}^*$).

Further details on the reduction procedures, together with some numerical examples, can be found in Refs [24-25].

3.3 Equivalent stress computation

Once the reduction procedures are performed, the rainflow counting method is applied to N_j^* -series. In particular, for each z -th counted reversal, the maximum value of N_j^* -series ($N_{max,z}^*$) is registered, and a new series of \mathbf{C} amplitude ($C_{a,z}^*$) is computed as a function of the components $C_{u,j}^*$ and $C_{v,j}^*$. By exploiting the above $N_{max,z}^*$ and $C_{a,z}^*$ values, the amplitude of the equivalent stress, related to the z -th reversal, can be computed as follows:

$$\sigma_{eq,a,z} = \sqrt{\left(N_{max,z}^*\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{af,-1}}{\tau_{af,-1}}\right)^2 \left(C_{a,z}^*\right)^2} \quad (4)$$

3.4 Damage and fatigue life estimation

Finally, the fatigue damage accumulated during T_0 is evaluated by means of the Palmgren-Miner rule, and more precisely:

$$D(T_0) = \sum_{z=1}^Z \frac{1}{2 \cdot N_0 \left(\frac{\sigma_{af,-1}}{\sigma_{eq,a,z}} \right)^k} \quad (5)$$

where Z is the total number of counted reversals. The fatigue lifetime, T_{cal} , can be, hence, computed as follows:

$$T_{cal} = D_{cr} \cdot \frac{T_0}{D(T_0)} \quad (6)$$

being D_{cr} the critical damage. Note that, it is experimentally proved that the critical damage is a random parameter that may range from 0.15 to 1.06 [24].

4. FREQUENCY-DOMAIN CRITERION

The time-domain criterion presented in **Section 3** has been subsequently reformulated in the frequency domain [23,26-29]. The main steps of the present frequency-domain criterion are depicted in **Figure 6**.

In order to perform the fatigue analysis, some input data are required, and more precisely:

- the fatigue material properties, that is: $\sigma_{af,-1}$, at N_0 , k , and $\tau_{af,-1}$;
- the applied loading conditions, that is: the matrix of the Power Spectral Density Functions (PSDFs), \mathbf{S}_{xyz} , of the applied random stress state and the observation time interval T_0 .

The main steps of the present criterion are discussed in detail in the following Sub-Sections.

Figure 6.

4.1 Critical plane determination

In order to determine the critical plane orientation (i.e. the crack initiation path) with respect to the averaged principal stress directions, let us consider a fixed frame XYZ with its origin in P (**Figure 6**). The stress tensor at point P can be described by:

$$\mathbf{s}_{xyz}(t) = \{s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4, s_5, s_6\}^T = \{\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z, \tau_{xy}, \tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}\}^T .$$

By considering the assumption that the stress tensor can be represented by a six-dimensional ergodic stationary Gaussian stochastic process with zero mean values, the matrix of Power Spectral Density Functions (PSDFs), $\mathbf{S}_{xyz}(\omega)$, is expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{S}_{xyz}(\omega) = \begin{bmatrix} S_{1,1} & S_{1,2} & S_{1,3} & S_{1,4} & S_{1,5} & S_{1,6} \\ S_{2,1} & S_{2,2} & S_{2,3} & S_{2,4} & S_{2,5} & S_{2,6} \\ S_{3,1} & S_{3,2} & S_{3,3} & S_{3,4} & S_{3,5} & S_{3,6} \\ S_{4,1} & S_{4,2} & S_{4,3} & S_{4,4} & S_{4,5} & S_{4,6} \\ S_{5,1} & S_{5,2} & S_{5,3} & S_{5,4} & S_{5,5} & S_{5,6} \\ S_{6,1} & S_{6,2} & S_{6,3} & S_{6,4} & S_{6,5} & S_{6,6} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

being ω the pulsation.

Then, a rotated frame $\hat{1}\hat{2}\hat{3}$ (with its origin in P), connected with the averaged principal Euler angles $\hat{\phi}, \hat{\theta}, \hat{\psi}$ (**Figure 6**), is considered and the stress tensor at point P can be described by:

$$\mathbf{s}_{\hat{1}\hat{2}\hat{3}}(t) = \{s'_1, s'_2, s'_3, s'_4, s'_5, s'_6\}^T = \{\sigma_{\hat{1}}, \sigma_{\hat{2}}, \sigma_{\hat{3}}, \tau_{\hat{1}\hat{2}}, \tau_{\hat{1}\hat{3}}, \tau_{\hat{2}\hat{3}}\}^T . \quad \text{More precisely, the } \hat{1}\text{-axis}$$

(defined by the two Euler angles $\hat{\phi}, \hat{\theta}$) is determined so that s'_3 experiences its maximum value in a statistical sense:

$$E \left[\max_{0 \leq t \leq T_0} s'_3(t) \right] \cong \sqrt{\lambda_0} \sqrt{2 \ln(N_1)} + \frac{0.5772}{\sqrt{2 \ln(N_1)}} \quad (8)$$

where λ_0 is the spectral moment of order 0 of the PSDF $S_{3',3'}$:

$$\lambda_0 = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} S_{3',3'}(\omega) d\omega \quad (9)$$

and $N_1 = \nu_0^+ T_0$, being ν_0^+ the expected rate of mean zero-upcrossings of s'_3 .

Then, the angle $\hat{\psi}$ is determined so that the variance of s'_6 is maximised:

$$\max_{0 \leq \psi \leq 2\pi} [\text{Var } s'_6] = \left[\max_{0 \leq \psi \leq 2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} S_{6',6'}(\omega, \hat{\psi}) d\omega \right] \quad (10)$$

and, hence, the $\hat{3}$ -axis (defined by $\hat{\psi}$) is obtained.

The PSDF matrix, $S_{\hat{1}\hat{2}\hat{3}}(\omega)$, with respect to the above rotated frame $\hat{1}\hat{2}\hat{3}$ can be computed by means of the rotation matrix $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{C}(\hat{\phi}, \hat{\theta}, \hat{\psi})$ [28]:

$$\mathbf{S}_{\hat{1}\hat{2}\hat{3}}(\omega) = \mathbf{C} \mathbf{S}_{xyz}(\omega) \mathbf{C}^T \quad (11)$$

Then, the normal to the critical plane, \mathbf{w} , is determined by using the same procedure proposed for the time-domain criterion (see Sub-Section 3.1).

4.2 Determination of the matrix of the Power Spectral Density functions related to the critical plane

Once the critical plane, Δ , is determined, a local frame uvw with its origin in P is adopted (see the red frame in **Figure 6**) and the stress tensor at the above point can be described by: $\mathbf{s}_{uvw}(t) = \{s_1'', s_2'', s_3'', s_4'', s_5'', s_6''\}^T = \{\sigma_u, \sigma_v, \sigma_w, \tau_{uv}, \tau_{uw}, \tau_{vw}\}^T$. In particular, the u -axis defines the direction maximizing the variance of s_6'' :

$$\max_{0 \leq \gamma \leq 2\pi} [\text{Var } s_6''] = \left[\max_{0 \leq \gamma \leq 2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} S_{6'',6''}(\omega) d\omega \right] \quad (12)$$

being γ the angle between the u -axis and the averaged principal stress direction $\hat{2}$ (**Figure 6**).

The matrix of the PSDFs, $\mathbf{S}_{uvw}(\omega)$, with respect to such a local frame can be computed by means of the rotation matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{C}} = \tilde{\mathbf{C}}(\gamma, \delta)$ [28]:

$$\mathbf{S}_{uvw}(\omega) = \tilde{\mathbf{C}} \mathbf{S}_{\hat{1}\hat{2}\hat{3}}(\omega) \tilde{\mathbf{C}}^T \quad (13)$$

4.3 Equivalent PSDF computation

In order to reduce the multiaxial stress state to an equivalent uniaxial one, an equivalent PSDF, S_{eq} , related to the critical plane is computed through the following linear combination:

$$S_{eq} = S_{3'',3''} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{af,-1}}{\tau_{af,-1}} \right) S_{6'',6''} \quad (14)$$

4.4 Damage and fatigue life estimation

Finally, the fatigue damage per unit time, $E[D]$, can be evaluated by employing a linear cumulative damage rule:

$$E[D] = \nu_a C_\sigma^{-1} \int_0^{+\infty} s^k p_a(s) ds \quad (15)$$

being ν_a the expected rate of occurrence of loading cycles, k and C_σ the parameters of the S-N curve under fully reversed normal stress ($\sigma^k N = C_\sigma$), and $p_a(s)$ the probability distribution of the amplitude (s) of the counted equivalent stress cycles. It deserves to be mentioned that the damage relationship (Eq. (15)) depends on the algorithm used to count the loading cycles, i.e. it is related to the method adopted for $p_a(s)$ estimation.

By considering the rainflow counting method, Dirlik proposed the following relationship for the probability distribution $p_a^{RFC}(s)$ [22]:

$$p_a^{RFC}(s)_{DK} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda_0}} \left[\frac{D_1}{Q} e^{-\frac{Z}{Q}} + \frac{D_2 Z}{R^2} e^{-\frac{Z^2}{2R^2}} + D_3 Z e^{-\frac{Z^2}{2}} \right] \quad \text{with } Z = \frac{s}{\sqrt{\lambda_0}} \quad (16)$$

where D_1 , D_2 , D_3 , Q and R are fitting parameters depending on the first four spectral moments of S_{eq} . Then, the expected fatigue damage per unit time can be expressed as follows:

$$E[D_{RFC}^{DK}] = \nu_p C_\sigma^{-1} (\sqrt{\lambda_0})^k \left[D_1 Q^k \Gamma(1+k) + (\sqrt{2})^k \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{k}{2}\right) (D_2 |R|^k + D_3) \right] \quad (17)$$

where Γ is the gamma function and v_p is the expected rate of peaks computed by means of the spectral moments of order 2 and 4 of the PSDF S_{eq} [24]. The fatigue lifetime, T_{cal} , can, hence, be computed as follows:

$$T_{cal} = \frac{D_{cr}}{E\left[D_{RFC}^{DK}\right]} \quad (18)$$

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present Section, the results in terms of both fatigue lifetime and crack initiation path determined by applying both the time-domain criterion (**Section 3**) and the frequency-domain one (**Section 4**) are shown and compared to the experimental ones described in **Section 2**. For both the fatigue criteria, the lifetime is computed by considering a critical damage, D_{cr} , equal to 1 (according to the Palmgren-Miner rule).

5.1 Time domain

The Probability Density Function (PDF) of $\sigma_{eq,a,z}$ (Eq. (4)) is plotted in **Figure 7** for each loading condition examined (see **Table 3**). It can be observed that the PDF of $\sigma_{eq,a,z}$ changes its shape by varying the loading ratio, $\lambda = \sigma_{z,max} / \tau_{yz,max}$.

Figure 7.

In **Table 4**, the theoretical results in terms of both fatigue lifetime and orientation of the normal to the crack initiation path are listed for all the loading conditions. In particular, the estimated fatigue lifetime, T_{cal} , is computed by means of Eq. (6), whereas the orientation of the normal to the crack initiation path, α_{cal} , is derived from the direction cosine of the normal \mathbf{w} to the critical plane with respect to Z -axis (i.e. the longitudinal axis of the specimen, see **Figure 2**). It is important to highlight that the different tests performed at the same loading ratio λ are represented, according to the present criterion, by only one value of T_{cal} and α_{cal} .

By comparing the results in **Table 4** with those reported in **Table 3**, it can be observed a good agreement between the estimated values and the experimental ones in terms of both fatigue lifetime and orientation of the crack initiation path. In particular, for a correct comparison of the crack initiation paths, it is also necessary to consider the value of the experimental scatter band of α_{exp} , being very large for some loading conditions (see the loading conditions Nos R6, R8, R10, R12 and R13 in **Table 3**). For loading conditions Nos R3, R4, R5, R9 and R11, α_{cal} values are quite different with respect to α_{exp} . Regarding the other loading conditions, the relative difference between α_{cal} and α_{exp} values is always lower than 20%.

Table 4.

The comparison between the estimated, T_{cal} , and the experimental, T_{exp} , fatigue lifetime is also shown in **Figure 8**. In particular, for each loading condition, the averaged value of the experimental fatigue lives (reported in **Table 3**) is considered. Note that the dashed lines correspond to the scatter band with a factor 2 (i.e. $T_{exp}/T_{cal}=2$ and 0.50), whereas the dash-dot lines correspond to the scatter band with a factor 3 (i.e. $T_{exp}/T_{cal}=3$ and 0.33).

Figure 8.

The above graph proves that the present time-domain criterion provides results mainly falling within the scatter band with a factor 2, independent of the applied loading ratio λ . More precisely, 77% of the results are included into scatter band with a factor 2, whereas all the results fall within the scatter band with a factor 3.

In order to assess the validity of the present time-domain criterion, the theoretical results are compared with those derived through three different fatigue criteria available in the literature **[30,41,42]**, and more precisely: the maximum normal stress criterion, the maximum shear stress criterion and the maximum normal and shear stresses criterion. The above criteria, formulated in the time-domain, implement the damage accumulation method in order to

determine the critical plane orientation. Further details on the results obtained by means of the above criteria can be found in Ref. [30].

In particular, the above comparison is statistically interpreted by means of the root mean square (RMS) error method [43], where the root mean square error, T_{RMS} , is determined through the following relationship:

$$T_{RMS} = 10^{E_{RMS}} \quad (19)$$

where E_{RMS} related to fatigue lifetime is computed as follows:

$$E_{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{l=1}^{13} \log^2 (T_{exp}/T_{cal})_l}{13}} \quad (20)$$

whereas that related to the orientation of the normal to the crack initiation path:

$$E_{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{l=1}^{13} \log^2 (\alpha_{exp,max}/\alpha_{cal})_l}{13}} \quad (21)$$

being $\alpha_{exp,max}$ the upper bound of the α_{exp} range reported in **Table 3**.

Figures 9(a) and **(b)** show the T_{RMS} values related to the fatigue lifetime and the orientation of the normal to the crack initiation path, respectively, in accordance with both the present time-domain criterion and other three literature criteria (that is, the maximum

normal stress criterion, the maximum shear stress criterion and the maximum normal and shear stresses criterion) [30,41,42].

Figure 9.

The analysis of the results in terms of T_{RMS} values clearly indicates that:

- for the estimations in terms of fatigue lifetime (**Figure 9(a)**), higher accuracy is gained by applying the present time-domain criterion, with a decrease of the T_{RMS} value up to 76% with respect to that deduced through the maximum normal stress criterion;

- for the estimations in terms of orientation of the normal to crack initiation path (**Figure 9(b)**), the most accurate results are determined by employing the present time-domain criterion, with the T_{RMS} value decreasing up to 92% in comparison with that determined with the maximum normal stress criterion.

5.2 Frequency domain

The one-sided Power Spectral Density Function (PSDF), $2S_{eq}$, of the equivalent normal stress (Eq. (14)) is plotted in **Figure 10** for each loading condition examined (see **Table 3**). It can be observed that the PSDF changes its shape by varying the loading ratio λ and it is in general characterised by five frequency peaks.

Figure 10.

In **Table 5**, the theoretical results in terms of both fatigue lifetime and orientation of the normal to the crack initiation path are listed for all the loading conditions. In particular, the estimated fatigue lifetime, T_{cal} , is computed by means of Eq. (18), whereas the orientation of the normal to the crack initiation path, α_{cal} , is obtained in the same way already presented for the time-domain criterion.

By comparing the results in **Table 5** with those reported in **Table 3**, it can be observed a good agreement between the estimated values and the experimental ones, especially in terms of fatigue lifetime. As far as the crack initiation paths are concerned, α_{cal} values are quite different with respect to α_{exp} for loading conditions Nos R4, R6, R7, R9, R10, R12 and R13; for the other examined loading conditions, the α_{cal} results are well correlated with α_{exp} ones, with a relative difference lower than 30%.

Table 5.

The comparison between the estimated, T_{cal} , and the experimental, T_{exp} , fatigue lifetime is also shown in **Figure 11**.

Figure 11.

The above graph proves that the present frequency-domain criterion provides results falling within the scatter band with a

factor 3, independent of the applied loading ratio λ . More precisely, 54% of the results are included into scatter band with a factor 2, whereas all the results fall within the scatter band with a factor 3.

As already presented for the time-domain criterion, the theoretical results of the present frequency-domain criterion are compared with those derived through: the maximum normal stress criterion, the maximum shear stress criterion and the maximum normal and shear stresses criterion [30,41,42]. In particular, **Figures 12 (a)** and **(b)** show the T_{RMS} values related to the fatigue lifetime and the orientation of the normal to the crack initiation path, respectively, in accordance with both the present frequency-domain criterion and the other three literature criteria.

Figure 12.

The analysis of the results in terms of T_{RMS} values clearly indicates that:

- for the estimations in terms of fatigue lifetime (**Figure 12 (a)**), similar accuracy is noticed by using the present criterion and the maximum shear stress criterion; moreover, the present criterion provides a decrease of the T_{RMS} value up to 71% with respect to that deduced through the maximum normal stress criterion;

- for the estimations in terms of orientation of the normal to crack initiation path (**Figure 12 (b)**), slightly better accuracy is reached by means of the maximum shear stress criterion, characterized

by a lower T_{RMS} value than that determined through the present criterion; however, the present criterion involves a decrease of T_{RMS} value up to 85% in comparison to the value obtained by using the maximum normal stress criterion.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper, the capability of two fatigue criteria in both estimating the fatigue life and predicting the crack initiation path of metallic components under random loading has been investigated. In particular, an experimental campaign performed at the Opole University of Technology on a construction steel 10HNAP, under biaxial non-proportional random loading, has been simulated by means of both a time-domain criterion and a frequency-domain one. Both criteria, proposed in the recent past by some of the present authors, are based on the so-called critical plane approach.

The agreement between experimental data and theoretical results has been quite satisfactory for both the time-domain and the frequency-domain criteria, and more precisely:

- for the estimations of fatigue lifetime, all the results related to both time-domain and the frequency-domain criteria are included into scatter band with a factor 3, and the T_{RMS} values are lower than 2;

- for the estimations of the orientation of the normal to crack initiation path, better results are obtained by employing the time-domain criterion, with a T_{RMS} value lower than 2, whereas the

frequency-domain criterion provides an higher T_{RMS} value ($T_{RMS} = 2.35$).

The accuracy of the present fatigue criteria has been also confirmed by means of the comparison with the results obtained through three other fatigue criteria, available in the literature and based on the critical plane approach. As a matter of fact, the most accurate estimations in terms of both fatigue lifetime and orientation of the normal to crack initiation path are always determined by means of the present time-domain criterion. Moreover, for the frequency-domain criterion, the obtained accuracy level is very similar to that achieved by using the maximum shear stress criterion, but much greater than that obtained with the other two criteria available in the literature.

Based on such encouraging results, it can be concluded that both the present criteria can be considered as promising engineering tools for fatigue design of metallic components under random loading, being able to correctly predict not only the fatigue lifetime but also the crack initiation path.

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NOMENCLATURE

\mathbf{C}	shear stress vector acting on the critical plane Δ
$C_{a,z}^*$	shear stress amplitude related to the z-th reversal
D	damage
D_{cr}	critical damage
$E[D]$	fatigue damage per unit time
$E[D_{RFC}^{DK}]$	expected damage per unit time by employing the RFC method according to Dirlik proposal
k, C_σ	coefficients of the S-N curve under fully reversed normal stress
\mathbf{N}	normal stress vector related to the critical plane Δ
$N_{max,z}^*$	normal stress maximum value related to the z-th reversal
N_0	reference number of loading cycles
$p_a(s)$	probability distribution of the amplitude (s) of the counted equivalent stress cycle
$r_{\sigma_z \tau_{yz}}$	cross-correlation coefficient between the normal and shear stress
\mathbf{s}_{xyz}	stress vector referred to the frame $PXYZ$
$\mathbf{s}_{\hat{1}\hat{2}\hat{3}}$	stress vector referred to the frame $P\hat{1}\hat{2}\hat{3}$
\mathbf{s}_{uvw}	stress vector referred to the frame $Puvw$
S_{eq}	equivalent PSDF
\mathbf{S}_{xyz}	PSDF matrix of \mathbf{s}_{xyz}
$\mathbf{S}_{\hat{1}\hat{2}\hat{3}}$	PSDF matrix of $\mathbf{s}_{\hat{1}\hat{2}\hat{3}}$
\mathbf{S}_{uvw}	PSDF matrix of \mathbf{s}_{uvw}

\mathbf{S}_w	stress vector related to the critical plane Δ
t	time
T_{cal}	estimated fatigue lifetime
T_{exp}	experimental fatigue lifetime
T_{RMS}	Root mean square error
T_0	observation time interval
uvw	local frame
\mathbf{w}	normal vector to the critical plane
W	weight function
XYZ	fixed frame
$\hat{1}, \hat{2}, \hat{3}$	averaged principal stress directions
α_{cal}	estimated orientation of the normal to the crack initiation path
α_{exp}	experimental orientation of the normal to the crack initiation path
γ	angle between the u -axis and the averaged direction $\hat{2}$
δ	angle between the averaged direction $\hat{1}$ and the normal \mathbf{w} to the critical plane
Δ	critical plane
λ_i	spectral moment of order i
μ_{σ_z}	variance of the applied normal stress, σ_z
$\mu_{\sigma_z \tau_{yz}}$	covariance of the applied normal, σ_z , and shear, τ_{yz} , stress

$\mu_{\tau_{yz}}$	variance of the applied shear stress, τ_{yz}
ν_a	expected rate of occurrence of loading cycles
ν_p	expected rate of occurrence of peaks
$\hat{\phi}, \hat{\theta}, \hat{\psi}$	averaged principal Euler angles
σ_{af-1}	fatigue strength at the reference number of loading cycles, N_0 , for fully reversed normal stress
$\sigma_{eq,a,z}$	equivalent shear stress amplitude related to the z-th reversal
σ_z	applied normal stress
$\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$	principal stresses
τ_{af-1}	fatigue strength for fully reversed shear stress
τ_{yz}	applied shear stress
ω	pulsation
$\sqrt{\mu_{\sigma_z}}$	standard deviation of the applied normal stress, σ_z
$\sqrt{\mu_{\tau_{yz}}}$	standard deviation of the applied shear stress, τ_{yz}

REFERENCES

- [1] Mahmud M, Abdullah S, Singh SSK, Ariffin AK, Nopiah ZM, Arifin A. Distribution characterisation of coil spring strain histories using mixed weibull analysis. *Int J Eng Technol (UAE)* 2018;7:110-117.
- [2] Kong YS, Abdullah S, Schramm D, Omar MZ, Haris SM. Vibration fatigue analysis of carbon steel coil spring under various road excitations. *Metals* 2018;8:617.
- [3] Chin CH, Abdullah S, Singh SSK, Ariffin AK, Schramm D. Probabilistic-based fatigue reliability assessment of carbon steel coil spring from random strain loading excitation. *J Mech Sci Technol* 2022;36:109-118.
- [4] Manouchehrynia R, Abdullah S, Singh SSK. Fatigue-based reliability in assessing the failure of an automobile coil spring under random vibration loadings. *Eng Fail Anal* 2022;131:105808.
- [5] Zhou ST, Chiu YJ, Lin IH. The parameters optimizing design of double suspension arm torsion bar in the electric sight-seeing car by random vibration analyzing method. *Shock Vib* 2017;59:8153756.
- [6] Hamzi NM, Singh SSK, Abdullah S, Azman AH, Rasani MRM. Durability assessment of automobile suspension lower arm under random road loads in time-frequency domain. *J Fail Anal Prev* 2021;21:1973-1980.
- [7] Mallor C, Calvo S, Núñez JL, Rodríguez-Barrachina R, Landaberea A. A probabilistic fatigue crack growth life approach to the definition of inspection intervals for railway axles. *Frat ed Integrità Strutt* 2021;16:359-373.
- [8] Gao JW, Dai GZ, Li QZ, Zhang MN, Zhu SP, Correia JAFO, Lesiuk G, De Jesus AMP. Fatigue assessment of EA4T railway axles under artificial surface damage. *Int J Fatigue* 2021;146:106157.
- [9] Hu Y, Qin Q, Wu S, Zhao X, Wang W. Fatigue resistance and remaining life assessment of induction-hardened S38C steel railway axles. *Int J Fatigue* 2021;144:106068.
- [10] Li F, Wu H, Liu C, Wu P, Zeng J. Vibration fatigue analysis of high-speed railway vehicle carbody under shaking condition. *Veh Syst Dyn* 2021.
- [11] You T, Zhou J, Gong D, Sun Y, Li B, Chen J. Synthesis of random vibration environment spectra for the fatigue analysis and optimization of railway vehicles. *Int J Fatigue* 2022;159:106752.
- [12] Singh SSK, Abdullah S, Nikabdullah N. The needs of understanding stochastic fatigue failure for the automobile crankshaft: a review. *Eng Fail Anal* 2017;80:464-471.
- [13] Infante V, Freitas M, Fonte M. Failure analysis of a crankshaft of a helicopter engine. *Eng Fail Anal* 2019;100:49-59.
- [14] Bulut M, Cihan O, Temizer I. Fatigue life and stress analysis of the crankshaft of a single cylinder diesel engine under variable forces and speeds. *Materials Testing* 2021;63:770-777.
- [15] Tomevenya KM, Liu SJ. Probabilistic fatigue-creep life reliability assessment of aircraft turbine disk. *J Mech Sci Technol* 2018;32:5127-5132.
- [16] Gao H, Wang A, Zio E, Bai G. An integrated reliability approach with improved importance sampling for low-cycle fatigue damage prediction of turbine disks. *Reliab Eng Syst Saf* 2020;199:106819.

- [17] Niu XP, Wang RZ, Liao D, Zhu SP, Zhang XC, Keshtegar B. Probabilistic modeling of uncertainties in fatigue reliability analysis of turbine bladed disks. *Int J Fatigue* 2021;142:105912.
- [18] Mršnik M, Slavič J, Boltežar M. Frequency-domain methods for a vibration-fatigue-life estimation - application to real data. *Int J Fatigue* 2013;47:8-17.
- [19] ASTM E 1049. Standard practices for cycle counting in fatigue analysis. 1990.
- [20] Palmgren A. Die lebensdauer von kugellagern. *VDI-Zeitschrift*, 1924;68:339-341.
- [21] Miner MA. Cumulative damage in fatigue. *J Appl Mech* 1945;12:A159-A164.
- [22] Dirlik T. Application of computers in fatigue analysis. PhD thesis. University of Warwick (UK); 1985.
- [23] Carpinteri A, Spagnoli A, Vantadori S. A review of multiaxial fatigue criteria for random variable amplitude loads. *Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct* 2017;40:1007-1036.
- [24] Vantadori S, Iturrioz I, Ronchei C. Discussion on fatigue life estimation under multiaxial random loading: comparison between time- and frequency-domain approach. *Theor Appl Fract Mech* 2018;96:134-145.
- [25] Vantadori S, Iturrioz I, Carpinteri A, Greco F, Ronchei C. A novel procedure for damage evaluation of fillet-welded joints. *Int J Fatigue* 2020;136:105599.
- [26] Ronchei C, Vantadori S, Carpinteri A, Iturrioz I, Issopo Rodrigues R, Scorza D, Zanichelli A. A frequency-domain approach for damage detection in welded structures. *Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct* 2021;44:1134-1148.
- [27] Carpinteri A, Fortese G, Ronchei C, Scorza D, Vantadori S. Spectral fatigue life estimation for non-proportional multiaxial random loading. *Theor Appl Fract Mech* 2016;83:67-72.
- [28] Vantadori S, Haynes R, Fortese G, Habtour E, Ronchei C, Scorza D, Zanichelli A. Methodology for assessing embryonic cracks development in structures under high-cycle multiaxial random vibrations. *Fatigue Fract Eng Mater Struct* 2018;41:20-28.
- [29] Vantadori S, Carpinteri A, Fortese G, Ronchei C. Influence of random fatigue loading non-proportionality on damage. *Theor Appl Fract Mech* 2018;96:56-63.
- [30] Marciniak Z, Rozumek D, Macha E. Verification of fatigue critical plane position according to variance and damage accumulation methods under multiaxial loading. *Int J Fatigue* 2014;58:84-93.
- [31] EN 10025-1. Hot rolled products of structural steels - Part 1: General technical delivery conditions. 2004.
- [32] EN 10025-5. Hot rolled products of structural steels - Part 5: Technical delivery conditions for structural steels with improved atmospheric corrosion resistance. 2019.
- [33] Rozumek D, Marciniak Z. Control system of the fatigue stand for material tests under combined bending with torsion loading and experimental results. *Mech Syst Signal Process* 2008;22:1289-1296.

- [34] Rozumek D, Marciniak Z, Lachowicz CT. The energy approach in the calculation of fatigue lives under non-proportional bending with torsion. *Int J Fatigue* 2010;32:1343-1350.
- [35] Macek W, Marciniak Z, Branco R, Rozumek D, Królczyk GM. A fractographic study exploring the fracture surface topography of S355J2 steel after pseudo-random bending-torsion fatigue tests. *Meas: J Int Meas Confed* 2021;178:109443.
- [36] Vantadori S, Carpinteri A, Luciano R, Ronchei C, Scorza D, Zanichelli A, Okamoto Y, Saito S, Itoh T. Crack initiation and life estimation for 316 and 430 stainless steel specimens by means of a critical plane approach. *Int J Fatigue* 2020;138:105677.
- [37] Ronchei C, Vantadori S. Notch fatigue life estimation of Ti-6Al-4V. *Eng Fail Anal* 2021;120:105098.
- [38] Vantadori S, Ronchei C, Scorza D, Zanichelli A, Carpinteri A. Fatigue behaviour assessment of ductile cast iron smooth specimens. *Int J* 2021;152:106459.
- [39] Vantadori S, Ronchei C, Scorza D, Zanichelli A, Araújo LC, Araújo JA. Influence of non-metallic inclusions on the high cycle fatigue strength of steels. *Int J Fatigue* 2022;154:106553.
- [40] Carpinteri A, Ronchei C, Scorza D, Vantadori S. Critical Plane Orientation Influence on Multiaxial High-Cycle Fatigue Assessment. *Phys Mesomech* 2015;18:348-354.
- [41] Karolczuk A, Macha E. Critical planes in multiaxial fatigue of materials. *Fortschritt-Berichte VDI, Mechanik/Bruchmechanik, reihe 18, nr. 298*. Dusseldorf: VDI Verlag; 2005.
- [42] Marciniak Z, Rozumek D, Macha E. Fatigue lives of 18G2A and 10HNAP steels under variable amplitude and random non-proportional bending with torsion loading. *Int J Fatigue* 2008;30:800-813.
- [43] Walat K, Łagoda T. Lifetime of semi-ductile materials through the critical plane approach. *Int J Fatigue* 2014;67:73-77.

**AN EFFICIENT TIME-DOMAIN FATIGUE ANALYSIS AND ITS COMPARISON TO
SPECTRAL FATIGUE ASSESSMENT FOR CONSTRUCTION STEEL 10HNP**

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FIGURES AND TABLES

Table 1. Chemical composition (in weight percentage) [30].

MATERIAL	C	Mn	Si	P	S	Cr	Ni	Cu	Fe
10HNAP	0.11	0.52	0.26	0.098	0.016	0.65	0.35	0.26	Balance

Table 2. Tensile and fatigue properties [30].

MATERIAL	E [GPa]	ν [-]	G [GPa]	σ_y [MPa]	σ_u [MPa]	A_{10} %	Z %	$\sigma_{af,-1}$ [MPa]	k [-]	$\tau_{af,-1}$ [MPa]	N_0 [cycles]
10HNAP	215	0.29	83.33	418	566	30.7	36.5	300	9.50	150	$3.135 \cdot 10^6$

Figure 1. Material microstructure.

Figure 2. Specimen geometry (sizes in mm).

Figure 3. Fatigue testing stand MZGS-200PL developed at the Opole University of Technology [30,33-35].

Table 3. Maximum value and standard deviation related to the normal and shear stress signals, σ_z and τ_{yz} , for each loading configuration examined. The number of tests and the corresponding fatigue life, T_{exp} , together with the orientation of the normal to the crack initiation path, α_{exp} , are also reported.

LOADING CONDITION	No. TESTS	$\sigma_{z,max}$	$\tau_{yz,max}$	λ	$\sqrt{\mu_{\sigma_z}}$	$\sqrt{\mu_{\tau_{yz}}}$	T_{exp}	α_{exp}
		[MPa]	[MPa]	[-]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[s]	[°]
R1	4	475	90	0.189	183.76	31.41	17460	49 (± 3)
							10200	
							19440	
							17520	
R2	5	475	130	0.274	185.32	47.74	13380	49 (+5;-2)
							11100	
							13080	
							10080	
R3	4	475	170	0.358	185.33	60.78	8940	48 (± 2)
							6720	
							9780	
							9060	
R4	3	475	210	0.442	182.51	74.04	5520	48 (+1;-2)
							5640	
							6660	
R5	3	420	90	0.214	170.38	31.85	293280	47 (± 1)
							204360	
							208620	
R6	4	420	130	0.309	159.20	49.65	226740	54 (+15;-9)
							154740	
							267540	
							180420	
R7	3	420	170	0.405	170.38	62.14	45780	52 (+8;-7)
							85020	
							60720	
R8	3	420	210	0.500	168.25	82.08	17820	54 (+16;-7)
							15780	
							12540	
R9	3	330	130	0.394	137.52	49.23	509820	47 (± 1)
							543900	
							599100	
R10	3	330	170	0.515	133.96	62.14	135720	68 (+12;-8)
							230460	
							418260	
R11	6	330	210	0.636	134.62	83.17	31560	47 (+1;-2)
							33780	
							68580	
							55500	
							44220	
R12	2	250	170	0.680	96.25	57.55	81660	82 (± 11)
							362220	
R13	4	250	210	0.840	91.00	79.83	483780	58 (+15;-11)
							74880	
							77760	
							74160	
							60120	

Figure 4. PDFs of the input signals σ_z and τ_{yz} , for each loading condition examined from (a) R1 to (o) R13 in Table 3.

Figure 5. Flowchart of the time-domain criterion.

Figure 6. Flowchart of the frequency-domain criterion.

Figure 7. PDF of the equivalent stress, $\sigma_{eq,a,z}$, for each loading conditions examined from (a) R1 to (o) R13 in Table 3.

Table 4. Estimated fatigue life and orientation of the normal to the crack initiation path, for each loading condition examined.

LOADING CONDITION	T_{cal} [s]	α_{cal} [°]
R1	19668	54
R2	35474	63
R3	12212	67
R4	13677	68
R5	189454	58
R6	76316	63
R7	69167	69
R8	18818	71
R9	617920	66
R10	175898	71
R11	40943	78
R12	320251	79
R13	90246	80

Figure 8. Comparison between the experimental lifetime data and the estimated fatigue lifetime, for each loading configuration examined.

Figure 9. T_{RMS} values computed by applying the present time-domain criterion, the maximum normal stress criterion, the maximum shear stress criterion, and the maximum normal and shear stresses criterion [30,41,42] related to: (a) the fatigue lifetime and (b) the orientation of the normal to the crack initiation path.

Figure 10. One-sided PSD function, $2S_{eq}$, for each loading conditions examined from (a) R1 to (o) R13 in Table 3.

Table 5. Estimated fatigue life and orientation of the normal to the crack initiation path, for each loading condition examined.

LOADING CONDITION	T_{cal} [s]	α_{cal} [°]
R1	20005	61
R2	15619	41
R3	24992	61
R4	2012	21
R5	510629	61
R6	95034	41
R7	20945	11
R8	26678	61
R9	1406089	71
R10	304944	51
R11	80857	61
R12	461886	31
R13	75016	11

Figure 11. Comparison between the experimental lifetime data and the estimated fatigue lifetime, for each loading configuration examined.

Figure 12. T_{RMS} values computed by applying the present criterion, the maximum normal stress criterion, the maximum shear stress criterion, and the maximum normal and shear stresses criterion [30,41,42] related to: (a) the fatigue lifetime and (b) the orientation of the normal to the crack initiation path.

